

Bridgehead Nitrogen Heterocycles. Synthesis and various Reactions of 5-(2-Morpholinoquinoxaline-3-yl)-4-amino-3-mercapto-4H-1,2,4-triazole

P. S. FERNANDES* and T. M. SONAR

N. S. Research Laboratories, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-400 001

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4-Amino-3-mercapto-5-(2-morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole (1), prepared by treating 2-morpholinoquinoxaline-3-acid hydrazide successively with CS_2 -KOH and NH_2NH_2 , gives the nitrogen bridge head fused heterocycles 2, 3, 4 and 6 on reacting with CS_2 , RCOOH , PhCONCS and PhCOCH_2Br , respectively.

THE present study is in continuation of our earlier work^{1,2} on the synthesis of various heterocycles derived from quinoxaline derivatives having pharmacological activities. Triazoles have significant antifungal, antibacterial, antiinflammatory, hypocholesteremic and hypotensive activities³⁻⁶. Encouraged by the earlier results, we report herein the synthesis of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-(2-morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole (1) and a few new bridgehead nitrogen heterocycles therefrom.

2-Morpholinoquinoxaline-3-acid-hydrazide¹ was reacted with carbon disulphide in ethanolic KOH to yield the potassium salt of the corresponding 3-aryoldithiocarbazate in quantitative yield. This when reacted with hydrazine hydrate (99%) in water gave the desired compound (1). The latter with CS_2 in pyridine gave the fused heterocycle (2). Condensation of 1 with either benzoin or ethyl acetoacetate according to the literature procedures^{5,7} was abortive. Compound 1 reacted with various carboxylic acids in the presence of POCl_3 giving the thiadiazoles (3) in fairly good yields. Compound 1 on condensation with phenacyl bromide followed by basification with K_2CO_3 gave the expected thiadiazine (6). Benzoylisothiocyanate gave with 1 the triazolothiadiazole (4) that resisted hydrolysis to 5 by liquor ammonia⁸.

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- 2: X=SH
3a: X=H
3b: X=Me
3c: X=Et
3d: X=Ph
4: X=NHCOPh
5: X=NH₂

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 633 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl_3) on a Varian FT 80 (60 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard, and mass spectra on a Varian 114 MAT instrument. All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

5-(2-Morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-4-amino-3-mercapto-4H-1,2,4-triazole (1): 2-Morpholinoquinoxaline-3-acid hydrazide (5.46 g, 0.02 mol) was added to ethanolic KOH (absolute alcohol 100 ml, KOH 1.683 g, 0.03 mol) at room temperature. To it carbon disulphide (2.3 g, 0.03 mol) was added and the mixture stirred at room temperature for 15 h when a saffron coloured product precipitated out. The mixture was diluted with diisopropyl ether (100 ml) and stirred further for 1 h. The separated solid was filtered, washed with diisopropyl ether and dried at 60° for 10 h, (7.5 g, 97%), m.p. 148° d; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 440 (NH), 1 640 (C=O) and 1 260 cm^{-1} (C=S). The potassium salt was used for the next stage without further purification.

Hydrazine hydrate (99%) (20.5 g, 0.64 mol) was gradually added to the above potassium salt (7.74 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in water (80 ml) with stirring and the mixture was refluxed gently for 2.5 h, during which period hydrogen sulphide evolved and the colour of the reaction mixture changed to green. The resulting solution was diluted with water (25 ml), cooled to 5° and acidified with concentrated HCl (35%) to pH 1.00 when a pale lemon-yellow solid separated out. It was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from alcohol to afford the triazole (1; 4.04 g, 61.4%), m.p. 216°; ν_{max} 3 340, 3 105 (NH_2), 2 830 (SH), 1 565 (C=N) and 1 450 cm^{-1} (C-N); δ 3.4 (4H, t, CH_2NCH_2), 3.75 (4H, t, CH_2OCH_2), 5.65 (2H, s, exchangeable, NH_2), 7.1-8.1 (4H, m, ArH), (SH proton could not be located in the spectrum); m/e 329 (M^+).

3-Substituted-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazol-6-(5H)-thione (2; thioamide form): A solution of 1 (0.5 g, 0.0015 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) was treated

with CS₂ (1 ml) dropwise with stirring at room temperature. The mixture was then gently heated in an oil-bath at 100° for 6 h with continuous stirring. Pyridine was removed in vacuum and the residue dissolved in benzene (5 ml) and diluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) (20 ml). The separated product was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethyl acetate (charcoal) to give the thiadiazole (2) as faint greenish prisms (0.34 g, 61%), m.p. 220°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 140 (C=S), 1 480, 1 540 (C–N), 1 610 (C=N) and 3 000–3 300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 3.35 (4H, t, CH₂NCH₂), 3.70 (4H, t, CH₂OCH₂), 5.60 (1H, s, SH) and 7.3–8.1 (4H, m, ArH).

5-(2-Morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazoles (3): Typical procedure: Compound 1 (0.329 g, 0.001 mol), formic acid (0.5 ml, 100%) and POCl₃ (5 ml) were heated together at 100° for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, crushed ice (~40 g) added to it and pH of the mixture was brought to 7 by adding liquor ammonia. It was then diluted with water (50 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was extracted with ethyl acetate (4 × 150 ml). The combined organic extract were dried (Na₂SO₄) and concentrated under vacuum. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethyl acetate–*n*-hexane to give 3a as yellow powder (0.18 g, 54%), m.p. 139°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 665 (C=N) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 2.7 (1H, s, NCH), 3.35 (4H, t, CH₂NCH₂), 3.70 (4H, t, CH₂OCH₂), and 7.25–8.25 (4H, m, ArH).

In the above reaction, when the formic acid was replaced by acetic acid, propionic acid and benzoic acid, compounds 3b (m.p. 97°), 3c (m.p. 171°), and 3d (m.p. 164°), respectively, were obtained in ~55% yield.

6-Benzoylamino-3-(2-morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazole (4): To a stirred solution of ammonium thiocyanate (0.12 g, 0.0015 mol) in acetone (15 ml) was added dropwise benzoyl chloride (0.15 g, 0.001 mol). The mixture was stirred for 15 min and treated with a solution of compound 1 (0.329 g, 0.001 mol) dissolved in acetone (50 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 3 h, then acetone was distilled off, cooled to room

temperature and diluted with ice-cold water (~25 ml). On scratching, solid mass appeared, which was filtered, washed successively with sodium bicarbonate solution and cold water, dried and crystallised (aqueous acetone), to give the thiadiazole (4; 0.34 g, 74%), m.p. 240°; $\nu_{\max}$ 3 020–3 160 (NH) and 1 670 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

3-(2-Morpholinoquinoxalin-3-yl)-6-phenyl-7H-s-triazolo[3,4-b][1,3,4]thiadiazine (6): A mixture of 1 (0.329 g, 0.001 mol), phenacyl bromide (0.2 g) in absolute ethanol (100 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 h. Activated charcoal was then added and the mixture refluxed further for 30 min and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated to about 30 ml and cooled to room temperature. To it solid K₂CO₃ was added with stirring till pH 7.5–8.00 and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated under vacuum and the resulting gummy mass extracted with ethyl acetate (7 × 20 ml). The combined ethyl acetate extracts was dried (Na₂SO₄) and then concentrated under vacuum to about 10 ml. To it was added *n*-hexane (20 ml), and the resulting dark yellow solid was filtered and crystallised from ethyl acetate–*n*-hexane to afford the thiadiazine (6; 0.21 g, 49%), m.p. 126°; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 550 (C–N), 1 590 (C=N) and 1 630 (C=C) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 3.45 (4H, t, CH₂NCH₂), 3.75 (4H, t, CH₂OCH₂), 4.1 (2H, s, SCH₂) and 7.15–8.20 (9H, m, ArH).

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